

“TECHNOLOGIES FOR DEVELOPING FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS’ COMPETENCE IN SELECTING CHILDREN FOR SPORTS”

Jalolova.Z.S, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University
Distance learning in social sciences and humanities
Department teacher.
+998904885889

Abstract: This article discusses modern pedagogical technologies for the formation and development of competence in the selection of children for sports among future physical education teachers. It also analyzes diagnostic methods used in the selection process for sports, selection criteria, and methods for developing the teacher's professional competencies.

Keywords: competence, sports qualification, pedagogical technology, diagnostics, physical training, specialization.

In the modern educational process, the ability of future physical education teachers not only to work with students, but also to perform important professional tasks such as identifying their sports potential, selecting, guiding and developing the right type of sport for them is of great importance. That is why the development of sports selection competence in teachers is an important indicator of the quality of education in the field of physical education and sports.

Future teachers need to have not only theoretical knowledge in their work, but also practical skills, assessment and selection competence. This article will extensively cover the content of sports selection competence, factors affecting it, and methods for developing competence based on modern technologies.

Content and tasks of the sorting competence. Selection competence is the teacher's ability to deeply analyze the individual physical and psychological state of children, select a suitable sport for them, guide them within their specialization, motivate them, and create conditions for the development of their sports potential. Selection competence includes the following elements: analysis of physical indicators (strength, endurance, coordination of movements), assessment of health and psychological state, determination of interest and motivation for sports, ability to work with individual approaches and selection criteria, documentation and analysis of one's own work. By forming this competence, the scope, effectiveness, and positive attitude of students to sports in physical education classes increase.

Factors to consider when selecting children for sports, the selection process is a multi-stage, complex and scientifically based activity. The following main criteria are taken into account in this process: anthropometric indicators, height, weight, body condition, body mass index, physical qualities, speed, agility, strength, endurance, elasticity, coordination of movements, the ability to quickly and correctly perform complex exercises, health status: cardiovascular system, respiratory organs, general condition, psychological state, stress tolerance, motivation, ability to work in a team, social factors, family environment, parental approach, socio-economic conditions. The relative level of these factors varies for each sport, for example, strength and endurance are important for weightlifting, and agility and coordination are important for gymnastics.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

Formation of competence based on modern pedagogical technologies The following technologies are recommended for developing the competence of future physical education teachers: modular teaching technology, which allows the teacher to choose individual development paths; case study: develops problem-solving skills through the analysis of real situations; observation-based practice (practicums) to study the selection process based on observation in sports schools or specialized classes; simulation games and role-playing exercises to train teachers by imitating sports selection processes; information and communication technologies, which allow digitization and analysis of selection data through fitness programs, online assessment systems, smart applications (for example, "FitnessGram", "SmartCoach").

The importance of selection competence in teaching The competence of a physical education teacher in sports selection plays an important role not only in identifying sports reserves, but also in forming a healthy lifestyle, supporting children's interests, and their social adaptation. Well-formed competence allows the teacher to: determine an individual sports direction for each student, reduce errors in sports selection, increase student motivation, systematically form sports reserves, and effectively organize pedagogical communication with parents.

The formation of the competence of future physical education teachers to select sports is an educational process that combines modern pedagogical technologies, diagnostic methods and practical activities, which not only ensures success in sports, but is also an important factor in raising a healthy and active generation. Therefore, the development of this competence should be systematically implemented through curricula, lesson content and practical exercises.

References:

1. Kadyrov BK "Theory and Methodology of Physical Education and Sports", Tashkent, 2021.
2. Mahmudov A. "Sports selection and its methodological foundations", Samarkand, 2022.
3. Nurmatov D. "Innovative approaches in the professional training of future physical education teachers", Ilm sarchashmalari, 2023.
4. Gulomov O. "Modern technologies in developing the competence of physical education teachers", Journal of Pedagogy, 2022.
5. Sports Science Journal (2020). "Talent Identification and Sports Selection in Children".